

PHILOLOGY

LITERARY ASSOCIATIONS OF THE UZBEKS IN KAZAKHSTAN

Mashakova A.

*PhD Philology, Leading researcher,
M.O. Auezov Institute of Literature and Art,
Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan*

Abstract

The article presents the diversity of literary process in Kazakhstan, which is a multinational country. More than 130 nations and ethnic groups live in peace and harmony on Kazakh soil. Uzbek writers, who live compactly in the South Kazakhstan region and create their works in the Uzbek language, bring their own unique flavor. A distinctive feature of the literary process in Kazakhstan is the existence of Uzbek literary associations in Kazakhstan: "Chashma", "Chimkent", "Sairam", "Isfijob", "Shuhla", "Kudrat Hikmat", "Kukkiyo ilhomlari", "Kamolot", "Karvon", "Atoyi", "Shamchirok". Each of them has its own history of formation and development, but they are united by common goals - promotion of peace, friendship, tolerance and mutual understanding of the nations and ethnic groups living in the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Keywords: Kazakhstan, literary associations, the Uzbeks, writers, poets.

The modern literary process in Kazakhstan has its own characteristic features, due to the diverse national composition of Kazakhstani writers and poets. The Uzbek writers also make a significant contribution to the development of Kazakhstani literature.

In our country, the Uzbeks live mainly in the southern region. According to the latest census, the number of ethnic Uzbeks in the Republic of Kazakhstan is up to 460 thousand people. There are the Uzbek theatre, television and radio broadcasting in the Uzbek language [1]. More than ten newspapers in the Uzbek language and three magazines are published in the South Kazakhstan region [2].

There are Uzbek national cultural centers in Kazakhstan, in particular in Shymkent, Kyzylorda, Almaty, Taldykorgan, Astana, Karaganda [3]. A distinctive feature is the existence of a number of Uzbek literary associations in Kazakhstan: "Chashma", "Sairam", "Isfijob", "Shuhla", "Kudrat Khikmat", "Kukkiyo Ilkhomlari" etc. Each of them has its own history of formation and development, but they are all united by common goals - promotion of peace, friendship, tolerance and mutual understanding of the nations and ethnic groups living in the Republic of Kazakhstan through their literary creativity. Uzbek-speaking writers and poets strive to raise worthy youth, to educate them in a patriotic spirit.

In 1987, literary association was created in the Sairam district of the South Kazakhstan region on the initiative of the creative intelligentsia. It was called "Chashma" ("The Spring") as a symbol of purity and a source of creativity and inspiration. "Chashma" was supported by the district newspaper "Mehnat Bairogi" and its editor Yusufzhon Saidaliyev. At that time, the works of the members of the literary association were published in this newspaper for the first time. Now this newspaper has been renamed "Sairam Sadosi", and it continues to publish the works of the writers of "Chashma".

The first leader of "Chashma" was the poet Irisali Zhumanov. He successfully led this literary association until 1992 and was able to gather around himself many

young representatives of creative youth. As I. Zhumanov began working in the editorial office of the regional newspaper "Dustlik Bayrogi" (now "Zhanubiy Kozogiston"), the activities of "Chashma" continued without the leader. Members of "Chashma" discussed their works at the meetings and published them in the local newspapers and magazines. In 1998, the poet Abdurakhim Pratov became the Chairman of the literary association "Chashma". The activities of the literary association intensified, many fans of creativity joined its ranks. In 2003, the district literary association "Chashma" received regional status. Members of the South Kazakhstan branch of the Writers' Union of Kazakhstan: Doctor of Philology Kerimbek Syzdykov, writers Marhabat Baygut, Abilda Aimak, Yersin Kuibagarov and Khanbibi Yesenkarayeva after meeting with the staff of the literary association and familiarization, discussion of their works, they unanimously decided to assign "Chashma" the status of a regional literary association. Currently, the organization has about 40 members of the literary association.

At the folk art festivals "Sairam Talantlari" held in 2001, 2002 and 2003, members of "Chashma" Soatoy Kamolova, Umrioy Karimova, Tilobat Pirnazarova, Guliosiy Khasanova, Shoakhmad Shopulatov and Bakhodir Otash took first place. At the same time, "Chashma" members actively took and take part in creative competitions "Nazm yulduzlari" ("Poetry Stars"), "Ofarin!" ("Bravo!"), receive various diplomas, certificates of appreciation and valuable gifts. The artworks of "Chashma" members are published in such Uzbek and Kazakh periodicals as the magazines "Mushtum" (Tashkent), "Alem Adebieti" (Astana), "Dala" (Almaty), "Gulistan" (Almaty), newspapers "Kishlok Hayoti" (Tashkent), "Ishonch" (Tashkent), "Ontustik" Kazakhstan" (Shymkent), "Zhanubiy Kozogiston" (Shymkent) and in a number of publications of the Sairam region of the South Kazakhstan region: the magazine "Boychechak", the newspapers "Zhanub Zharchilari", "Martube", "Sairam Sadosi", "Zhamiyat va Marifat", "Sairam Sabosi", "Bolajon", "Isfijob", "Adabiyot va Sanjat".

In 2001-2012, the poetic and prose creative writings of this literary association were published in joint collections "Kanot Kokdi", "Tuyona", "Turon Chechaklari", "Chashma Guldasi", "Chashma Mavzhilari", "Yoshlar Ovozi". At the same time, the most active members of "Chashma" - Sunnatulla Akramov, Irisali Zhumanov, Soatoy Kamolova, Umriy Karimova, Guli Osiyo, Bakhodir Otash, Abdurakhim Pratov, Oituti Rezhametova, Shoahmad Shopulatov and Dilnoza Rustambekova published their own collections of works. At present, the writers of "Chashma" have published about twenty books, which are warmly received by the readers.

The members of the literary association have translated the works of a number of Kazakh writers and poets into Uzbek and published them in local newspapers and magazines. Literary evenings and meetings of the readers with the well-known writers of Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan are held. The literary association "Chashma" and its members actively cooperate with teams of other creative associations of Southern Kazakhstan. They constantly share experiences, hold joint literary events, poetry competitions. During nine years the "Argumok" Literary Prize ("Race Horse"), established by them, has been awarded to the best writers.

Members of "Chashma" are actively involved in public activities in the regional Uzbek ethno-cultural center. Writers and poets Sunnatulla Akramov, Soatoy Kamolova, Umriy Karimova, Abdurakhim Pratov and Tilobat Pirmazarova were awarded "Zhamoat fakhriysi", "Zhamoat fidoyisi" medals of the "Dustlik" Association of the Uzbeks of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

In 2012, the literary association "Chashma" celebrated its 25th anniversary. Officials, the Kazakh writers and guests from the neighboring Republic of Uzbekistan attended the ceremonial meeting dedicated to this significant event at the regional Uzbek drama theater. Israil Saparbayev from the Union of Writers of the Republic of Kazakhstan from Almaty, Abilda Aimak and Yersin Kuybagarov from the branch of the South Kazakhstan region have attended the event. The creative delegation of Uzbekistan was headed by the prominent writer Nosir Fozilov, twice laureate of the State Prize of the Republic of Uzbekistan, laureate of the Peace and Spiritual Accord Prize of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan. In his opinion, "the literary and creative association "Chashma" had a very positive impact on the development and creative growth of Uzbek literature in the Republic of Kazakhstan. The writers of "Chashma" made a great contribution to strengthening the friendship of the fraternal Uzbek and Kazakh peoples and development of relations between Uzbek and Kazakh literatures".

Currently the literary association "Chashma" is a kind of school of literary excellence and a platform for sharing creative experience for its members and other people who are interested in creativity.

The literary association "Sairam" was created in 1979 in the Sairam district of the South Kazakhstan region. The poet Orifkhon Saidikramov was elected as Chairman, and Khavazmat Kuchkorov was elected as Secretary. Mirakhmad Butabekov and Anvar

Pardabekov headed the journalistic and poetry departments. A year later, this group was named as Yusuf Saremii "Sairam" creative association, and later the poet Anvar Pardabekov started his activities as the head of "Sairam". The active members of "Sairam" were the writers Kholbuvi Tillakhuzhayeva, Mukhiddin Kodirov, Khotam Yuldosh, Erkinoy Sultonova, Ikhtiyor Mamadaminov, Abdurakhim Pratov and Sayyora Ziyobekova. In the early 1990s, "Sairam" suspended its activities for various reasons, and resumed its work in the early 2000s. In 2010, Sulton Yuldosh headed the literary association "Sairam", and currently it is headed by Gayrat Rakhmetov.

In 2002 the literary association "Isfijob" was organized in the Sairam district of the South Kazakhstan region on the initiative of the poet Urmon Sobir, who still leads this group. The literary association is named after the poet Odilkhon Tillakhuzhaev. The leading member of this group is a member of the Union of Writers and the Union of Journalists of the Republic of Kazakhstan Havazmat Kuchkorov - the author of the books "Kosagulning hotini", "Ortda kolgan kunlar" and "Zhavokhira tatigulik umr". The books of Sobirjon Shomurodov "Umr utmokda", "Sirlil olam", Khurbuvi Odilova "Uylarim", Odilkhon Tillakhuzhaev "Armon kushi", Khurshid Kuchkorov "Mukhabbatni izlab" were also published. In 2013, joint collection of members of the literary association "Isfijob" was published in Almaty.

The literary associations "Kudrat Hikmat" and "Kukkiyo Ilhomlari" have been operating in the city of Turkestan for many years. "Kudrat Hikmat" is headed by the poet, member of the Union of Writers of the Republic of Kazakhstan Ernazar Ruzimetov. The organizer and head of "Kukkiyo Ilhomlari" is the employee of the newspaper "Turkiston" Akajon Izzatullaev. Members of the literary associations - Ernazar Ruzimetov, Olimjon Durjonboev, Ibokhim Pulat, Hamza Mirkhaydar, Dolimjon Saifullaev, Khusan Ubaidullaev, Akajon Izzatullaev, Sanzhar Gulomov are famous people of Turkestan city. Ernazar Ruzimetov became prominent during the Soviet period, and in 1974, he was accepted to the Union of Writers of the USSR, he published about twenty books for children and adults.

In 2012, the creative association "Shuhla" was created in the village of Korabulok in the Sairam district. Its organizers were local writers. "Shuhla" is headed by the poetess Gulnora Begaliyeva, and the literary scholar Rakhimtoy Begaliyev is the scientific adviser of this creative group. There are about twenty members in the "Shuhla". There are also creative associations "Kamolot" (headed by Mavluda Makhamedova) in the village of Kulkent in the Sairam district, "Karvon" (headed by Mirsibir Mirazizov) in the village of Ozodlik in the Tyulkubas district, "Atoi" (headed by Bakhodir Sobitov) in the village of Turbat in the Kazigurt district, "Shamchirok" (headed by Alisher Usmonov) in the Tulebi district.

Thus, among the Uzbek creative teams of Kazakhstan, the literary associations "Chashma", "Isfijob", "Sairam", "Kudrat Hikmat" and "Kukkiyo Ilhomlari"

are distinguished for their active work. Members of literary associations, being the authors of the works which are recognized by the readers, made a significant contribution to the development of Uzbek literature in the Republic of Kazakhstan.

It should be noted that the rise of the Uzbek literary associations falls on the period of independence of our country. During these years, the most active and talented Uzbek writers and poets Irisali Zhumanov, Khavazmat Kuchkorov, Bakhodir Sobitov, Abdurakhim Pratov and Zokirjon Muminjonov were accepted to the Union of Writers of the Republic of Kazakhstan. The books by Uzbek literary masters are published in printing and publishing houses of Almaty, Tashkent, Shymkent and the Sairam region, some of them have been translated into the Kazakh language. Thus, in 2009, a poetry collection by Abdurakhim Pratov, "Birtal gul" ("Bouquet of flowers"), was published in Almaty, which included selected poems of the poet which are translated into the state language by Israil Saparbayev. Such direction of creative activity as artistic translation is actively developing in the Uzbek literary environment of Kazakhstan. Abdurakhim Pratov, Zokirzhon Muminzhonov, Dolimzhon Saifullaev, Bakhodir Otash and Urmon Sobir successfully translated into Uzbek the works of Kazakh poets and prose writers Marhabat Baygut, Yersin Kuybagarov, Tynymbay Karin, Zhalel Kattabek and Kulbek Ergobek.

The Forum of Uzbek writers of Kazakhstan "Nazm yulduzlari" ("Poetry Stars"), which is established by the "Dustlik" Association of the Uzbeks of the

RK is annually held with the aim to provide spiritual encouragement and material support to Uzbek poets and writers. According to the Chairman of the Association, Ruzakul Kholmurodov, one of the main goals of this competition is to popularize the creativity of Uzbek writers: "We intend to publish a collection of poems by current Forum participants and distribute them among schools for use as a training manual" [4]. In 2003, the ceremony of opening of the Uzbek Regional Drama Theatre took place. The activities of this art center accompany the development of Uzbek literature in our country, since many dramatic works of Uzbek authors of Kazakhstan have been staged in this theatre and this tradition continues.

Uzbek literary associations hold various events aimed at sharing experience, professional training, and developing ties with colleagues from the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Uzbek poets and writers are doing their best to meet the demands of the current period in the field of literature.

References

1. The Uzbeks in Kazakhstan // <http://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki>
2. "Robita" – connecting thread of generations // <http://robita.ucoz.org/news/2011-11-01>
3. http://www.assembly.kz/userfiles/baza_dannyh_eko.pdf
4. "Poetry Stars" Forum was held in South Kazakhstan // <http://www.fergananews.com/news.php?id=4245>